

the major institutions (Singh & Sureja 2006). The study is the first attempt to document the cultural heritage of grinding stones practiced by the Shertukpen tribes of Northeast India from an ethnographic and anthropological view of point. The term 'grinding stone' in this paper refers to the stone tools that are used to grind and pound a variety of materials, most often cereals. Terminologies used in the study included traditional mills (rotary quern and nutting stone) and mechanical mills. The terms *Chakki* (rotary quern/millstone in Hindi), *Ran-thok* (a type of *Chakki* used by the Shertukpens) and *Ling-chhom* (nutting stone) have been used to represent the traditional mills.

Stone tools that played a crucial role in the daily life of hunter-gatherers, settled agriculturists, and pastoralists for centuries are used by few people in the world today. These tools are the fundamental component of food production necessary to human survival during the past years (Ebeling & Rowan 2004). The stone tools from Upper Paleolithic were used to process plant foods, and they constitute the earliest evidence for this activity (De Beaune 1993; Piperno *et al.* 2004). Such tool kits commonly include either saddle stones or rotary querns turned by hand (Revedin *et al.* 2010). Saddle querns are the most ancient and widely used type of quern-stone which was superseded around the 5th to 4th century B.C. by the more efficient rotary querns (McLaren & Hunter 2008). Rotary querns were a common type of mill in Europe and the Mediterranean basin during the middle iron age that was supposedly introduced from Spain (Curwen, 1937; Moritz, 1958: 109). The earliest published example of a rotary quern in the Middle East is from 1st Century A.D. Masada, Israel (Ebeling 2019). In Central Asia including India, the introduction of rotary querns has been determined by the Soviet scholars as 3rd and 4th Century A.D. (Stančo 2018). Rotary quern, which is based on the principle of a fixed lower stone and a rotating runner stone have changed very little in thousands of years (Catterall 1999; Rajasthan Agricultural Competitiveness Project 2019). On the other hand, stone tools used for nut-cracking are also known as pitted stone cobbles, anvil or nutting stones, pitted stone hammers and cupstones (M'guire 1891; Odell 1998; Adams 2002; Goren-Inbar *et al.* 2002; Roda Gilabert *et al.* 2012). Such stone tools have been presumed to be used prehistorically for crushing nuts such as hickory, etc. as foodstuffs (Walters *et al.* 2015). Nutting stones are typically small flat stones made of limestone, sandstone, or other sedimentary types of rock that could be carried by hand and the bottom stones have flat surfaces or feature one or more ground or pecked cups of various sizes, shapes, and depth (Davis 1995: 334). These stone tools have distinct local traditions laden with social as well as functional importance (Shoemaker *et al.* 2017). The surfaces of such objects may be intentionally modified during the manufacturing process, altered exclusively by use, or by a combination of these forces (Peterson 2008). Ethnographic studies documented the multiple functions of ground stone implements that are either related to or unrelated to food processing. For instance, mineral pigments, hides, small mammals, legumes, hydrophytic tubers, ferns, as well as a variety of substances for consumption such as coffee, sugar, chili, salt, and herbs (Adams 1988; Davis 1995; Dubreuil 2004; Fullagar *et al.* 2008; Hayden 1987; Jones 1986; Perry 2004; Yohe *et al.* 1991).

In India, *Chakki* is used to grind grains and spices. *Chapati* (in Hindi) or unleavened bread is the staple food of the majority of the population in the Indian sub-continent. It is popularly known as *Atta* (in Hindi) or wheat flour which is obtained by grinding wheat in *Chakki* (Haridas Rao *et al.* 1986). *Chakki* is attrition mill consisting of two circular stones mounted on a vertical axis which consists of a stationary stone cylinder upon which a smaller stone cylinder rotates (Barbosa-Canovas *et al.* 2006). The smaller ones, for household use,

are operated by two people and the larger ones for community or commercial purposes use livestock to rotate the upper cylinder (Yallappa *et al.* 2019).

Arunachal Pradesh is a diverse state of India in terms of ethnicity. The state is inhabited by about 26 major tribes and more than 100 sub-tribes. In addition to the Shertukpen other major tribes are the Adi, Aka, Apatani, Bugun, Digaru Mishmi, Galo, Hill Miri (Now Nyishi), Idu Mishmi, Khamba, Khampti, Memba, Miju Mishmi, Mishing, Monpa, Nocte, Nyishi, Puroik, Tagin, Tangsa, Singpho, Sajolang, Sartang, Wancho, Yobin, and Zakhring which makes the state panoramic and distinct from the other states. The Shertukpen tribe consists of small communities residing towards the far western corner of the state in the West Kameng district (Figure 1). Agriculture is the mainstay of life for the Shertukpens who practice both shifting and permanent cultivation. They are also keen traders. And while they have adopted Buddhism of the Mahayana sect, their religion is an interesting blend of Buddhism and Indigenous magico-religious beliefs. They are also good at wood carving and stone sculpting. The availability of raw materials such as stone and wood in the surroundings has encouraged the Shertukpen artisans to become skilled experts in making stone tools. Shertukpen livelihoods are heavily dependent on agriculture, and thus they have a long tradition of making stone tools to grind cereals like wheat, maize, millet, etc. which became invaluable to meet their food requirements. Here we attempt to document the significance of grinding stones to their livelihood, and also discuss the feasibility of improvements using modern technologies and the necessity of its preservation.

The study area is the West Kameng district of Arunachal Pradesh, Northeast India (Figure 1.) The district shares an international border with Tibet and Bhutan. The topography of the district is mostly mountainous with tangled peaks and valleys. Bichom, Dirang Chu and Tenga are the main rivers flowing through the district. The forest types of West Kameng range from tropical semi-evergreen to alpine, and they are a storehouse of more than 500 species of plants of medicinal and pharmacological significance. On average, the area receives 1743 mm of annual rainfall and has a mean monthly maximum and minimum temperature of 21.44° C and -1.24° C. West Kameng district has a total population of 87,013 (Census of India 2011). The inhabitants of the district are comprised mainly of Aka (Hrusso), Bugun (Khowa, Monpa), Sajalong (Miji), Sartang and Shertukpen ethnic groups. The Shertukpens largely depend on agriculture and animal products for their livelihood. The district is divided into 260 villages, 5 administrative blocks, and 13 administrative circles. The administrative circles of the district are Balem, Bhalukpong, Bomdila, Dirang, Jamiri, Kalaktang, Kamengbari-Doimara, Nafra, Rupa, Shergaon, Singchung, Thembang, and Thrizino.

Methods

The study is based on primary data collected through questionnaires, personal interviews and field observations that occurred during June and July 2019. A total sample of 120 households - 10 each from 12 Shertukpen inhabited villages - was randomly selected to carry out the survey. The names of the surveyed villages are Birpur, Brokpublang, Chillipam, Dikshipam, Gorbaw, Jigaon, Lumbaktang, Membachur, Mukuthing, Musakshing, Shergaon, and Thongre. The questionnaire consists of pertinent questions on the usage, manufacturers, manufacturing process, parts and function and other relevant information of grinding stones (Supplementary 1). The elderly people and artisans (above 60 years of age), both men and women,

Figure 1. Location map of the study area (Source: Bapu & Nimasow 2021)

were also interviewed to understand the history of grinding stones. Information on the significance of this practice and the materials used for grinding was also obtained through Focus Group Discussion with the villagers. Participant observation was another important tool for understanding the antique traditional grinding stones. Besides, the three surviving craftspeople have been interviewed to understand the entire process of manufacturing grinding stones. A simple *chaîne opératoire* (operational chain) was used by paying attention to the selection of raw materials, energy spent and techniques applied for shaping and converting a stone into usable products – *Ran-thok* and *Ling-chhom*. *Chaîne opératoire* is a means to break down each technological process into its elements (links in the chain). The interrelationships between the links of the chain focus on the technology itself, the socio-cultural, the political, and the ideological aspects that are expressed through human courses of action and speech (Leroi-Gourhan 1993).

Results

Manufacturing *Ran-thok* (rotary quern) and *Ling-chhom* (nutting stone)

The grinding stones are manufactured by specific professionals known as *Zyopo* (Figure 2) in the Shertukpen dialect. These tools are made for their own use and also sold to other members of the village on requisition. The interview with the surviving manufacturers reveals that the manufacturing process of grinding stones is an arduous and time-consuming task. The time taken in manufacturing these tools depends on the consistency and the number of men involved in the work. For example: when we asked about how long it took to make a *Ran-thok*, the answer during the interview ranged between one month if two to four men are involved and two months if the manufacturer works single-handedly every day. On the other hand, the manufacturing of *Ling-chhom* is easier and less time-consuming i.e. about 10 to 15 days of daily work. The manufacturing process involves the collection of raw materials, processing and finishing. The *Zyopos* informed during the interview that there are no differences between the villages in terms of the raw materials used in making stone tools. They collect ling-say (gneiss rock) from the surroundings as the preferential material for making the grinding stones. Such suitable stones are generally available in the area but sometimes they also excavate or break it from the rocks. Besides, the wooden mortar and pestle are made from *Pinus roxburghii* (pine tree) or *Castanopsis* spp. (oak tree), depending on the availability in the vicinity. The majority of the time is spent in the processing and finishing of the materials as they use

Figure 2. Rinchin Dorjee Megeji (*Zyopo*) at work
(Photo by K. D. Thongdok)

Figure 3(a). *Chapzee Achandu* **(b).** *Chapzee Odok* **(c).** *Nzongbee* **(d).** *Thung*
(Photo by K. D. Thongdok)

Table 1. Types of grinding tools, average size and raw materials used

Types of grinding stones	Parts	Average size (in cm)	Raw materials used
<i>Ran-thok</i> (Rotary quern)	Lower stone	Diameter = 40 Thickness = 10	Gneiss stone
	Upper stone	Diameter = 40 Thickness = 15	Gneiss stone
	Wooden plank	Length = 115 Breadth = 75	<i>Castanopsis</i> spp.
<i>Ling-chhom</i> (nutting stone)	Nutting stone	Length = 60 Width = 30 Height = 45	Gneiss stone
	Wooden pestle	Length= 150	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>

indigenous tools like hammer, hoe, chisel, etc. for shaping, polishing and finishing the grinding stones. These tools are made of iron with wooden and plastic handles. Name of some of the common tools in their dialect are *Chapzee Achandu* (Figure 3a), *Chapzee Odok* (Figure 3b), *Nzongbee* (Figure 3c), and *Thung* (Figure

3d). The mean size of the finished product slightly varies in different villages due to wear and tear during the manufacturing process. The details of stone tools, average mean size and raw materials used are shown in Table 1.

Parts and function of *Ran-thok* and *Ling-chhom*

The traditional *Ran-thok* (grinding stone) comes in pairs (Figure 4a). The base consists of wooden planks (made of *Castanopsis* spp.), 115cm x 75cm, which form a bent structure known as *bleng* (Figure 4b). The *bleng* stabilizes the stones while also collecting the flour that comes out of grinding. The rounded base or lower stone, diameter 40cm, thickness 10cm, and known as the *uukhu*, is stationary (Figure 4d). Above the lower stone is the *getheng* (upper stone), diameter 40cm, thickness 15cm. The *getheng* does the actual grinding (Figure 4c). The upper stone spins above the stationary lower stone creating the grinding action of the stones. It is generally slightly concave, while the lower stone is slightly convex. This helps to channel the flour that comes out of grinding to the outer edges of the stones where it can aggregate for collection. A wooden handle known as the *enyi* is fixed on a corner of the runner stone for turning it. A short lever on the centre of the lower stone connects with a small hole at the centre of the runner stone as a support for holding both the stones. A small hole is made on the upper stone where the grains are poured to be slowly ground. *Ran-thok* is mostly operated by the women either single or double in sitting gestures (Figure 5).

Figure 4(a). *Ran-thok* (b). *Bleng* (wooden plank) (c). *Getheng* (Upper stone) (d). *Uukhu* (lower stone) (e&f). *Ling-chhom* (nutting stone). Photo by N. J. Thongdok

Figure 5. Shertukpen woman grinding millet using *Ran-thok*
(Photo by N. J. Thongdok)

Figure 6. Shertukpen girl pounding corn grains in a nutting stone
(Photo by N. J. Thongdok)

There are two types of nutting tools used by the Shertukpens – one made of gneiss, known as *Ling-chhom* and another, made of wood, known as *Hing-chhom* (Figures 4e & 4f). The nutting stone is oval in shape with a length, width, and height dimensions of 60cm, 30cm, and 45cm, respectively. The wooden tool is 20cm in diameter and 60cm in height. Interactions with the villagers revealed that these tools were largely used for breaking corn grains into coarse-ground cornmeal and cracking nuts. The grains are put into the hole and pounded by a wooden pestle (made of *Pinus roxburghii*) known as *chang-khey* – which is about 150cm. Some nutting stones and pestles can be quite large. Generally, women either single or double in standing gesture pounds corn grains or crack nuts (walnut) in the *Ling-chhom* (Figure 6).

According to villagers, the use of these tools is not specific to them, as the neighboring tribes also used similar tools. During the survey, the grinding stones especially *Ran-thok* was observed in the majority of the households. The grinding and pounding activities are mostly performed by the women (Figure 5 & 6). However, it is not specific to them only as men occasionally help them. They further reported that the usage and importance of these grinding stones in recent years has declined due to convenient access to commercially produced flour and mechanical mills. Traditionally, wheat, millet, corn, and barley were important crops for food but nowadays rice and other readily available food items are preferred more by the younger generations. Consequently, changing food habits have limited the use of these tools to remote and inaccessible villages only. The villagers, particularly in rural areas, reported that they still largely depend on the grinding stones for processing food items as it is linked to their age-old tradition. They also reported that grinding and pounding activities provide opportunities for social interactions such as merrymaking, and performing folk songs with fellow friends. So, the interviewed villagers expressed interest to continue grinding and pounding practices into the future for both meeting food requirements and developing interpersonal relationships in traditional ways.

Discussion

The Shertukpens pay attention while sculpting and selecting the type of stones for easy and quick grinding of cereals as the right profile and accurate gap between the stones is important for the better quality of flour that comes out of grinding. However, the traditional grinding stones are increasingly lacking in proper sculpting and maintenance of the gap between the stones as the tools are very old and handed over from one generation to another generation. The accurate gap between the stones is an important consideration because *too big* a gap or *unbalanced stones* result in coarse or poorly ground flour. Through this study, it is learned that the manufacturing of grinding stones is a complex process that requires skills, knowledge and hard work. Nixon-Darcus & Meresa (2020) also reported similar findings in northeastern Tigrai. The study found that grinding traditions have been impacted by changing livelihoods and new grinding technologies. However, the villagers in rural areas have retained the use of some grinding stone tools despite these not always being the most efficient options. This is consistent with similar findings on grinding stone studies in Africa (Shoemaker *et al.* 2017). The stone used for a quern needs to be resistant to wear and durable. Generally, manual querns are made from different rock types; preferably of igneous origin. The reported use of gneiss in rotary querns by the Shertukpens conforms to the Celtic rotary querns of the Czech Republic

The possibilities of modifying indigenous grinding stones with modern power tools could be disseminated to the Shertukpens for sustaining such endangered material culture.

Glossary

Shertukpen

bleng
chang-khey
enyi
getheng
hing-chhom
ling-chhom
ling-say
ran-thok
Shertukpen
uukhu
zyopo

English

curved wooden plank
wooden pestle
wooden handle
upper stone
wooden nutting stone
nutting stone
gneiss rock
grinding stone
Indigenous tribal group, Arunachal Pradesh, India
lower stone
grindstone makers

Hindi

atta
chakki
chapati

English

wheat flour
mill stone
unleavened bread

Data accessibility

Data are available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5118675>

Supplementary material

Script and codes are available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5118675>

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Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors of this preprint declare that they have no financial conflict of interest with the content of this article.

Compliance with ethical standards

The methods used in the study conform to the relevant guidelines and regulations. The protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Rajiv Gandhi University, Itanagar, India (Ref. No. IEC/RGU/02). Both oral and written informed consent to participate was also obtained from all the respondents.

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List of supplementary files

Supplementary file 1

The supplementary file 1 contains the questionnaire used for data collection and the anonymized version of answers to the questionnaire.

Questionnaire filled with anonymized version of answers

1.0 IDENTIFICATION

- (a) District: **West Kameng**
- (b) Circle: **Rupa**
- (c) Name of the village: **Thongre**
- (d) Name of the respondent: **Phurpa Dorjee Thongchi**
- (e) Relationship of respondent with the head of household: **Self**
- (f) Age of respondent: **48 Years**
- (g) Educational qualification: Illiterate / Primary / **Secondary** / Graduate / PG / Professional
- (h) Religion: Hindu / **Buddhist** / Christian / Others, if any specify
- (i) Tribe / Sub-tribe: **Shertukpen**
- (j) Clan: **Thongchi**
- (k) Total number of family members:
 - (i) Below 14 years – **01**
 - (ii) Between 15 – 59 – **03**
 - (iii) Above 60 – **Nil**

2.0 INFORMATION ON GRINDING STONES

2.1 Usage of grinding stones

1. Do you use grinding stones? Yes/ No, if yes, then specify the types:

Yes, I use two types of grinding stones i.e. *Ran-thok* and *Ling-chhom*.

2. How long you are using the grinding stones? Please explain:

I had been using grinding stones since I inherited it from my grandparents.

3. Does every household in the village use the grinding stones? Please explain:

Most of the villagers used grinding stones but some of them do not possess grinding stones of their own. However, the villagers share and collectively use grinding stones in mutual understanding whenever the need arises.

4. Name the cereals/nuts that are ground using rotary querns/nutting stone.

Maize/ corn, barley, millet and wheat using rotary querns and Maize/ corn and walnut using nutting stone.

5. Who performs the grinding activity? Male/Female/Both

Most of the grinding activities are done by women but men also help occasionally.

2.2 Manufacturers and manufacturing process

1. Do you manufacture the grinding stones yourself? Yes/ No

2. Are there specific professional group that makes grinding stones? Please explain:

Yes, there are specific professional group known as *Zyopo* who are skilled in manufacturing grinding stones. Such skills are passed down from one generation to another. However, some people also learn these skills by regular practice and working with the skilled people.

3. Which stone is/are used for manufacturing the grinding stones? Please explain:

Most preferably Metamorphic rocks such as Gneiss due to its agile texture.

4. From where the stone and other raw materials obtained? Please explain:

The stones are collected from the nearby rocky mountains while the other raw materials like wood, bamboo, etc. are collected from the forests.

5. Are there differences in raw materials used between the villages? Please explain:

There are no differences in raw materials used between the villages. However, slight variations in hardness and texture of the stones and plant species used for making other parts of the grinding stones exists.

6. What are the tools/equipments used for making grinding stones? Please explain:

There are four common tools locally known as *Chapzee Achandu* (Hoe), *Nzongbee*, (Chisel) *Chapzee Odok* and *Thung* (Hammers).

7. Name the materials used in indigenous tools/equipments.

Iron, wood, plastic and cloth.

8. Could you please explain the stepwise procedure of making grinding stones?

**1. Collection of raw materials: Suitable stones are searched out in the vicinity and collected. In case the suitable stones are not available then it is excavated from the rocks.
2. Processing: Stones are broken down to desired shape and size using hammers, hoe and chisels.
3. Finishing: The final step involves shaping, designing, polishing and finishing the stones into rotary querns and nutting stones.**

9. Which step is the most time consuming and laborious? Please explain:

The whole process of manufacturing grinding stones is time consuming and laborious. However, the processing and finishing steps are most time consuming as indigenous tools are used. Besides, these steps need patience and perseverance.

10. How long it takes to make a rotary quern (*Ran-thok*)? Please explain:

One month if two to four men are involved and two months if the manufacturer works single-handedly every day. So it basically depends on the craftsperson, whether to take help from others or not.

11. How long it takes to make a nutting stone (*Ling-chhom*)? Please explain:

The manufacturing of nutting stone is easier and less time-consuming than rotary quern. It can be manufactured within 10 to 15 days of daily work.

12. What are the mean sizes of the finished products (*Ran-thok* and *Ling-chhom*)?

***Ran-thok* mean size: Lower stone diameter 40cm and thickness 10cm, Upper stone diameter 40cm and thickness 15cm; Wooden plank length 115cm and breadth 75cm.**

***Ling-chhom* mean size: Length 60cm, width 30cm and height 45cm; Wooden pestle length 150cm.**

13. Are there differences in the mean size of the grinding stones between the villages?

The mean size of the finished product slightly varies in different villages due to wear and tear during the manufacturing process.

14. Are these grinding stones sold or traded?

Yes, but rarely whenever there is a requisition from the villagers.

15. Do the manufacturing skills are inherited from generation to generation?

Yes, in majority of the cases the skills are inherited from the forefathers. However, some interested people learn the skills by working hard with the skilled and knowledgeable manufacturers.

2.3 Parts and function of *Ran-thok* and *Ling-chhom*

1. What are the different parts of *Ran-thok* (rotary quern)?

Usually *Ran-thok* (rotary quern) comes in pairs (a lower stone and an upper stone). The base consists of a wooden plank known as *Bleng*. A wooden handle known as *enyi* is fixed on a corner of the runner stone and a short lever on the centre of the lower stone connects with a small hole at the centre of the runner stone.

2. What are the materials used for different parts of *Ran-thok*?

Gneiss rock for lower and upper stones and *Castanopsis* spp. (tree) for wooden plank, handle and short level. *Castanopsis* spp. is preferred for its hollowness and hardness. However, other hard wood trees are also used in absence of preferred plant species.

3. What are the shape and sizes of different parts of *Ran-thok*?

**Lower stone: Rounded and slightly convex; mean size diameter 40cm, thickness 10cm.
Upper stone: Rounded and slightly concave; mean size diameter 40cm, thickness 15cm.
Wooden plank: Curved; mean size length – 115 cm and breadth – 75 cm).**

4. Whether men/women/both operates the *Ran-thok*?

***Ran-thok* is mostly operated by women either single or double. Men also help occasionally.**

5. What are the gestures of performing activity in *Ran-thok*?

It is performed in sitting gestures.

6. What are the types of *Ling-chhom* (nutting stone)?

There are two types of nutting tools namely *Ling-chhom* (nutting stone) and *Hing-chhom* (wooden mortar & pestle).

7. What are the different parts of *Ling-chhom*?

Nutting stone and a wooden pestle.

8. What are the materials used for different parts of *Ling-chhom*?

Gneiss rock for nutting stone and *Pinus roxburghii* (Chir pine) for wooden pestle.

9. What are the shape, length, width and height of the *Ling-chhom*?

Nutting stone: Oval; mean size length 60cm, width 30cm and height 45cm.

Wooden pestle: Elongated mean length 150 cm.

10. Whether men/women/both operates the *Ling-chhom*?

Generally, women operate the *Ling-chhom* either single or double. Sometimes men also help.

11. What are the gestures of performing activity in *Ling-chhom*?

It is performed in standing gestures.

12. Which plant species are used for making the wooden nutting tool?

There are no specific plant species for making wooden nutting tool. It can be made from any hard wood such as pine trees namely blue pine and chir pine.

13. Which grains and nuts are pounded using *Ling-chhom*?

Maize/ corn grains and walnuts.

2.4 Other information

1. Is the use of grinding stones specific to your village or tribe?

No, the use of these tools is not specific to us. It is also used by the neighboring tribes.

2. Whether the grinding practices are still prevalent in your village?

Yes, it is still practiced in my village but the usage and importance of these grinding stones has declined in recent years. At present very few people are using it.

3. What are the reasons for declining usage rate of stone tools these days in the society?

The reasons for declining usage rate of stone tools are convenient access to commercially produced flour and mechanical mills. Nowadays rice and other readily available food items are preferred more by the younger generations. The changing food habits have limited the use of these tools to remote and inaccessible villages only.

4. Is the grinding stone tools linked to your culture and tradition?

Yes, the grinding stones are very much linked to our age-old culture and tradition. Besides, grinding and pounding activities also provide us the opportunities for social interactions such as merrymaking and performing folk songs with fellow friends.

Thank you very much for your kind cooperation and patience.

Investigator: **Norbu Jamchu Thongdok**
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